

dl-Pentadecanol-2.—A mixture of myristic acid (11.4 g., 0.05*M*), lactic acid (9 g., 0.1 *M*), and Na (0.35 g., 0.015 g. atom) in 98% methanol (100 c.c.) was anodised at 1.5 to 1.7 amps. for 6 hrs. (theoretical time, 2.68 hrs.). Internal temperature was maintained between 30° and 35°. The anodised solution gave 4.2 g. hexacosaneⁿ, m.p. 60° (lit. m.p. 59-60°), 3.4 g. of butane-2,3-diol, b.p. 81-83°/12 mm (lit. b.p. 182.5°), and 2.55 g. of *dl*-penta decanol-2, b.p. 163-65°/12 mm. (Found: C, 78.8; H, 13.71. C₁₅H₃₂O requires C, 78.95; H, 14.03%). Acid phthalate, m.p. 57.58°. The final residue (3.4 g.) was not further worked up.

dl-Heptadecanol-2.—A mixture of palmitic acid (12.9 g., 0.05*M*), lactic acid (9.0 g., 0.1*M*), and Na (0.35 g., 0.015 g. atom) in 98% methanol (100 c.c.) was anodised at 1.5 to 1.7 amps. for 6 hrs. (theoretical time, 2.68 hrs.). Internal temperature was maintained at 40-50°. The anodised solution yielded 6.8 g. of triacontane, m.p. 68° (lit. m.p. 68°), 3.5 g. of butane-2, 3-diol, b.p. 81-83°/12 mm (lit. b.p. 182.5°), and 2.3 g. of *dl*-heptadecanol-2, b.p. 185-87°/2 mm (lit. b.p. 140°/0.5 mm). (Found: C, 79.20; H, 13.81. Calc. for C₁₇H₃₆O: C, 79.69; H, 14.07 %). Acid phthalate, m.p. 63°. The final residue (2.4 g.) was not further worked up.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
D.A.V. COLLEGE, KANPUR.

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Anodic Synthesis. Part II. Homopilosinic Acid and *dl*-Homopilopic Acid

J. K. Mehrotra and A. N. Dey

Homopilosinic acid has been prepared by hydrolysis of the corresponding substituted butyric acid. In view of the difficulty in separating the mixture of isomeric acids obtained during the preparation of homologues¹ of this acid, a method, partly based on electrolysis, has been employed with success.

Isopilocarpine, on oxidation with KMnO₄ (Jowett, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 77, 474, 851; 1901, 79, 581, 1331; Pinner, *ibid.*, 1903, 83, 438; Pinner *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1900, 33, 1424, 2357; 1901, 34, 727; 1902, 35, 204, 2443; 1905, 38, 2560), gives a mixture of pilopic acid (X: R=Et) and homopilopic acid (VII a: R=Et). Pilopic acid and isopilopic acid were synthesised by Tschitschibabin and Preobrashenski (*Ber.*, 1930, 63, 460) from diethyl formylsuccinate. Preobrashenske *et al.* (*Ber.*, 1936, 69, 1835; *Bull. Acad. Sci., U. S. S. R.*, 1936, 993) converted *dl*-pilopic acid via pilopyl alcohol, chloride, and nitrile to *dl*-homopilopic acid. Preobrashenski *et al.* (*Doklady, Acad. Nauk. S. S. S. R.*, 1951, 81, 613), following the above procedure, have prepared several homologues of homopilopic acid.

Independently, Dey (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1057) had prepared *dl*-homopilopic acid (VIIa: R=Et) and *dl*-homoisopilopic acid (VIIa: R=Et) by condensing ethyl γ -phenoxy-crotonate (I) with cyanoacetate and ethyl iodide and hydrolysing the substituted glutarate (II) formed.

Dey also prepared these acids by condensing ethyl 2-chloro-3-phenoxybutyrate (III), with ethyl malonate and ethyl iodide and hydrolysing the condensed product (IV):

As the removal of the phenoxy group requires higher temperatures causing isomerisation of the acids, Dey replaced it by OEt group.

In the present investigation substituted butyric acids have been used for the preparation of homolactonic acids. For this purpose, 1-chloro-3-ethoxypropan-2-ol (Fairbrowne *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2318) was converted into 1-cyano-3-ethoxypropan-2-ol (Lespieau, *Compt. rend.*, 1905, 140, 437) by boiling with ethanolic KCN. This was then dehydrated by P_2O_5 to 1-ethoxy-3-cyano-2-propene (V) (Lespieau, *ibid.*, p. 724) and the latter was finally condensed with diethyl malonate to obtain ethyl 1-ethoxycarbonyl 2-ethoxymethyl-3-cyanobutyrate (VI: R=H). On hydrolysis this gave homopilosinic acid (VIIa and VIIb: R=H).

To generalise this method for the preparation of homologues of this acid, the preparation of *dl*-homopilosinic acid was attempted. For this purpose (VI: R=H) was condensed with ethyl iodide. Ethyl 1-ethoxycarbonyl-1-ethyl-2-ethoxymethyl-3-cyanobutyrate (VI: R=Et), thus produced, was hydrolysed, yielding two isomeric acids (VIIa and VIIb: R=Et.) The esters of these acids could be separated from each other with difficulty. The same difficulty arose when, instead of ethyl iodide, benzyl chloride was used. In this case the yields were found to be very poor.

In a further attempt for the preparation of these acids, a method partly based upon anodic synthesis (this *issue*, p.885) has been utilised. Thus for the preparation of ethyl homopilosinate (XI: R=H), first pilosinic acid (X:R=H) was prepared. Diethyl 1-ethoxycarbonyl-succinate (VIII: R=H) (Michael, *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 3223) was condensed with monochloromethyl ethyl ether in dry benzene to produce diethyl 1-ethoxycarbonyl-1-ethoxymethyl-succinate (IX: R=H). The latter was hydrolysed to pilosinic acid (X: R=H). This, when electrolysed with ethyl hydrogen malonate, gave ethyl homopilosinate (XI: R=H) in 32.56% yield.

Similarly, for the preparation of ethyl *dl*-homopilosinate (XI: R=Et; yield 20%) by electrolysis, following analogous reactions but using diethyl 1-ethoxycarboxyl-2-ethylsuccinate (VIII: R=Et) (Bischoff and Hjett, *Ber.*, 1888, **21**, 2091), *dl*-pilopie acid (X:R=Et) was produced. This was then electrolysed with ethyl hydrogenmalonate. Thus electrolytic method has been found to be quite convenient for the preparation of this class of compounds, which are intermediates for the synthesis of the Jaborandi alkaloids.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 1-Ethoxycarbonyl-2-ethoxymethyl-3-cyanobutyrate.—To dry ethanol (100 c.c.) containing sodium (9.2 g.) was added diethyl malonate (80 g.). When the mixture had acquired the room temperature, 1-ethoxy-3-cyano-2-propene (45.5 g., b.p. 80-83°/15 mm) was added dropwise with stirring during 45 minutes. The mixture was gently refluxed for 1½ hours, cooled, and glacial acetic acid (25 g.) was added with stirring. After removal of the ethanol, the cooled residue was poured in 200 c.c. of water. The lower layer of the crude ester was separated and the aqueous layer extracted with CHCl₃. The combined organic liquid was dried over fused CaCl₂ and the solvent removed. The residue was fractionally distilled when after the forerun of diethyl malonate at 100°/20 mm, the bulk (105 g.) of ethyl 1-ethoxycarbonyl-2-ethoxymethyl-3-cyanobutyrate distilled at 192-99°/20 mm (b.p. 194-96°/20 mm); $d_{18.5}^{20}$, 1.0637; n_D^{20} —1.439. (Found: C, 58.1; H, 8.5. C₁₃H₂₁O₅N requires C, 57.56; H, 7.75%).

Homopilosinic Acid.—Ethyl 1-ethoxycarbonyl-2-ethoxymethyl-3-cyanobutyrate (60 g.) and HCl (conc., 120 c.c.) were gently refluxed for 8 hours on a low flame. The mixture was evaporated to dryness, water was added, and the whole was extracted with ether (30 c.c. × 2). The aqueous layer was treated with charcoal and again evaporated to dryness under diminished pressure. After desiccation for 24 hours, this was extracted with 50, 40, 30, 20, and 10 c.c. portions of ether, leaving NH₄Cl as the residue. The mixed ethereal layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and the solvent removed, when β-ethoxymethyl glutrate was obtained as a colorless viscous liquid (27 g.), soluble in water and ether; n_D^{25} 1.448. (Found: C, 50.61; H, 8.6. C₈H₁₄O₅ requires C, 50.53; H, 7.9%). This formed an anhydride on heating. This compound (10 g.) was refluxed with 48% HBr (40 g.) for 6 hours and then evaporated to dryness under diminished pressure till completely free of HBr fumes. The residue, dissolved in water (50 c.c.), was treated with charcoal and the clear aqueous layer was reduced to a small bulk and kept in a refrigerator overnight when crystalline homopilosinic acid was obtained (6.5 g.). This was recrystallised from water, m.p. 85-86° (lit. m.p. 86.5°). The mother liquor further gave 1.5 g. of the same compound. This is soluble in water and ether. (Found: C, 50.03; H, 5.51. Calc. for C₆H₈O₄: C, 50.0; H, 5.56%). Ethyl homopilopiate, b.p. 153-56°/6 mm. (Found: C, 55.7; H, 7.2. Calc. for C₈H₁₂O₄: C, 55.8; H, 6.98%).

Ethyl 1-Ethoxycarbonyl-1-ethyl-2-ethoxymethyl-3-cyanobutyrate.—To sodium (4.6 g.), dissolved in ethanol (75 c.c.), taken in a 500 c.c. three-necked flask, ethyl 1-ethoxycarbonyl-2-ethoxymethyl-3-cyanobutyrate (54.2 g.) was added with stirring. This was followed by dropwise addition of ethyl iodide (46.8 g.). The whole was refluxed for 2 hours and the unchanged EtI and ethanol were removed. The residue was poured in water (150 c.c.), the ester layer separated, and the aqueous layer extracted with ether (50 c.c.). The ether layer was mixed with the ester and the mixture was dried over fused CaCl₂. The solvent was removed and the bulk of the butyrate (48 g.) was collected at 178-82°/6 mm; $d_{22.6}^{22.6}$ 1.0419; n_D^{24} 1.4405. (Found: C, 60.94; H, 8.84; N, 4.61. C₁₅H₂₅O₅N requires C, 60.20;

H, 8.36; N, 4.68%). It is a light yellow liquid with characteristic odour of a nitrile; it is insoluble in water and soluble in organic solvents.

dl-Homopilopic Acid.—The above cyanobutyrate (30 g.) was refluxed with HCl (conc., 120 c.c.) for 12 hours and evaporated to dryness. The residue was kept in vacuum over solid KOH for 24 hours, extracted with dry ether, the ether removed, and the residue was refluxed with 48% HBr (40 c.c.) for 12 hours. HBr was completely removed under diminished pressure and the residual syrup (9 g.) containing a mixture of lactonic acids was kept over solid KOH in vacuum for several days. This was esterified with ethanol. The mixture of esters was fractionated and the fraction passing at 193-96°/4 mm, containing ethyl homopilopiate (lit. b.p. 210°/10 mm), was collected separately (7.5 g.). This fraction was re-fractionated several times. The ester thus obtained was hydrolysed by HCl (40 c.c.) to yield 5.9 g. of *dl*-homopilopic acid, m.p. 100°; b.p. 211-14°/4 mm (lit. m.p. 100-101°; b.p. 235-37°/20 mm). (Found: C, 56.6; H, 7.4. Calc. for $C_8H_{12}O_4$: C, 56.2; H, 7.07%).

Ethyl 1-ethoxycarbonyl-1-benzyl-2-ethoxymethyl-3-cyanobutyrate (b.p. 228-31°/2 mm) was prepared by using sodium (4.6 g.), ethyl 1-ethoxycarbonyl-2-ethoxymethyl-3-cyanobutyrate (54.2 g.), and benzyl chloride (38.0 g.) in 21.6 g. yield. (Found: C, 65.93; H, 7.48; N, 3.47. $C_{20}H_{24}O_5N$ requires C, 66.48; H, 7.48; N, 3.88%).

Attempted Method for 4-Benzylhomopilosinic Acid.—The above cyanobutyrate (25 g.) was first hydrolysed by HCl (conc., 130 c.c.). After removal of NH_4Cl , as described earlier, it was further hydrolysed by 48% HBr (40 g.). HBr was removed and the crude residue (3.9 g.) was esterified. From the mixture of esters no specific fraction could be obtained. (Found: C, 68.68; H, 6.70. $C_{15}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 68.70; H, 6.82%).

Diethyl 1-Ethoxycarbonyl-1-ethoxymethylsuccinate.—Sodium powder (2.3 g.) in dry xylol (100 c.c.) was treated with diethyl 1-ethoxycarbonylsuccinate (24.6 g., b.p. 156-57°/15 mm) (lit. b.p. 156-58°/15 mm) with vigorous stirring. When the reaction had subsided and whole of the sodium had dissolved, monochloromethyl ethyl ether (14.2 g.) was added during 30 mins. and the mixture left overnight. It was refluxed for 3 hours. The cooled opaque reaction mixture was poured in water (50 c.c.). The organic layer was washed with water (10 c.c. $\times$ 2) and dried over fused $CaCl_2$. The solvent was removed and the residue fractionated. The ester was collected at 160-63°/8 mm, yield 25 g. (Found: C, 54.9; H, 8.02. $C_{14}H_{24}O_7$ requires C, 55.26; H, 7.90%).

Pilosinic Acid.—Diethyl 1-ethoxycarbonyl-1-ethoxymethylsuccinate (10 g.) was refluxed with HCl (conc., 40 c.c.) for 6 hours when a homogeneous mixture was produced. The mixture was evaporated to dryness, the residue refluxed with 48% HBr (20 c.c.) for further 6 hours, and HBr was completely removed. The residue was dissolved in water (50 c.c.) and extracted with benzene (20 c.c.). The aqueous layer after decolorisation and evaporation from a water bath gave a residue, which, when recrystallised from water, gave 4 g. of pilosinic acid, m.p. 58.9° (lit. m.p. 57.8°). (Found: C, 45.7; H, 4.84. Calc. for $C_5H_6O_4$: C, 46.15; H, 4.62%).

Diethyl 1-Ethoxycarbonyl-1-ethoxymethyl-2-ethylsuccinate (50 g., b.p. 155-60°/4 mm) was prepared by following a procedure similar to that described above, using 4.6 g. of sodium powder, 55.0 g. of diethyl 1-ethoxycarbonyl-2-ethylsuccinate and 28.4 g. of monochloromethyl ethyl ether. (Found: C, 57.83; H, 8.25. $C_{16}H_{28}O_7$ requires C, 57.63; H, 8.43%).

dl-Pilopic acid was obtained by hydrolysing the preceding ester (66.5 g.) with HCl and HBr, as described above, in almost quantitative yield, m.p. 90-91° (lit. m.p. 90-91°). (Found: C, 53.0; H, 6.21. Calc. for $C_7H_{10}O_4$: C, 53.16; H, 6.33%). The ethyl ester, b.p. 300° (lit. b.p. 299°).

Ethyl Homopilosinate (Electrolytically).—A mixture of pilopic acid (6.5 g.), ethyl hydrogenmalonate (13.2 g.), and metallic sodium (0.35 g.) was electrolysed in methanolic solution, using the apparatus and procedure described in the previous communication (*loc. cit.*). A current of 1.5 amps. was passed for 3 hours and 30 minutes (theoretical time, 2.6 hours). The temperature of the reaction mixture was kept below 30°. The electrolysed solution yielded 4.2 g. of diethyl succinate, b.p. 217° (lit. b.p. 217°; by simple coupling), 2 g. of the residue, which had not been further worked up, and 2.8 g. of ethyl homopilosinate, b.p. 153-55°/6 mm (by cross coupling). (Found: C, 55.61; H, 6.83. Calc. for $C_8H_{12}O_4$: C, 55.81; H, 6.98%). Homopilosinic acid, m.p. 85-86° (lit. m.p. 86.5°).

Ethyl dl-Homopilopitate (Electrolytically).—A mixture of pilopic acid (15.8 g.), ethyl hydrogenmalonate (26.4 g.), and sodium (0.69 g.) in methanol was electrolysed by passing a current of 1.5 amps. for 7 hours (theoretical time, 5.3 hours). The temperature was kept below 30°. The electrolysed solution gave 9 g. of diethyl succinate, b.p. 217° (lit. b.p. 217°), 7 g. of the residue which was not further worked up, and 5.1 g. of ethyl *dl*-homopilopitate, b.p. 193-96°/4 mm (lit. b.p. 210°/10 mm.). (Found: C, 59.7; H, 7.9. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{16}O_4$: C, 60.0; H, 8.0 %). *dl*-Homopilopic acid, m.p. 100° (lit. m.p. 100-101°).